

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A PEDAGOGIC PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the effectiveness of organizing the educational process based on communicative competence in helping young people find their place in a rapidly developing social life and its impact on the socialization of the younger generation.

INTRODUCTION

In today's era of globalization, modernizing and rapidly developing social life, fundamentally reforming the education system has become a necessity of the times. Along with efficiently utilizing innovative pedagogical technologies in education, it is noted that merely developing students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in specific subjects is insufficient. Nowadays, it has become clear that possessing only subject-specific knowledge, skills, and abilities is no longer enough for students.

MAIN PART

As education is now envisioned to be organized based on a competency-based approach, let us examine the meaning of the term "competence." The word "competence" derives from "to compete," meaning "to contest," "to rival," or "to compete." Literally translated, it signifies "the ability to compete."

It is essential to distinguish between competencies and educational competencies. Educational competence models the student's future full-fledged activities. For example, a citizen may not be able to apply certain competencies until they reach a specific age. However, this does not mean such competencies should not be developed in students. In such cases, we speak of educational competence. For instance, although a student in school may acquire civic competence, they fully apply it only after graduating. Thus, these competencies manifest as educational competencies during the learning process.

There is no universal list of core competencies globally, as every country or region has its traditions, mentality, and specific requirements. Competence represents society's social order for its citizens, defined by the social environment of a particular country or region. Achieving such consensus is not always possible. For example, in the Swiss and U.S. joint project of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development and the National

Institute for Educational Statistics titled "Defining and Selecting Key Competencies," it was concluded that strictly defining core competencies is not always feasible.

Mastering one's native language and at least one foreign language to effectively engage in social communication;

Clearly and coherently expressing one's thoughts in oral and written forms, formulating logically sound questions and answers based on the topic;

Demonstrating social adaptability, adhering to cultural norms in communication, and working collaboratively;

Respecting the interlocutor's opinions during communication while defending and persuading others of one's position;

Managing emotions in conflicting situations and making necessary (constructive) decisions to resolve problems and disputes.

In the process of implementing a continuous education system, the importance of quality teaching and upbringing is emphasized. It is crucial to note that such a complex and multifaceted task can only be achieved with young teaching staff who possess high qualifications and pedagogical mastery.

Pedagogical mastery is not an innate talent or a hereditary trait; rather, it is based on research and creative labor. Therefore, pedagogical mastery is not a standardized or uniform teaching method applicable to all teachers. Instead, it is developed and refined through each teacher's individual research and creative efforts.

In this regard, it is necessary for one teacher to learn from the pedagogical mastery and experiences of others, to use them creatively, and to enrich their own teaching practices with advanced methods. A teacher's pedagogical mastery is most vividly demonstrated in classrooms and lecture sessions. This is because teaching sessions, by their very nature, are the core responsibility of teachers in educational institutions. Hence, they must be scientifically and ideologically sound, engaging, and closely linked to real life and the readiness level of students.

In the educational process, there must be a dynamic dialogue, mutual respect, and close collaboration between teachers and students to achieve the main objectives. Lessons that lack depth, are disconnected from practical experience and real life, consist of general advice and superficiality, or are conducted merely for formal purposes, do not interest students and fail to provide them with sufficient intellectual and ideological nourishment. Therefore, lessons should be organized in such a way as to foster diverse perspectives, critical thinking, and the formation of scientific beliefs among students.

Human beings solve all their tasks through communication. Addressing problems in life is closely linked to discussing them, explaining them to others, and reaching common understanding.

In today's world, where internationalization, globalization, and informatization trends are intensifying, preparing participants of the continuous education system for effective communication and improving the pedagogical mechanisms that develop their communication skills is of particular importance.

It is essential to view students not just as individuals who utilize language but as linguistic personalities who manifest their unique qualities through language, imbue it with national, cultural, and ethnic characteristics, preserve it, and pass it on to future generations.

In a system of continuous education, achieving this goal requires that graduates of any educational institution possess not only professional competencies but also communicative skills. These skills must form during schooling and later develop in accordance with the student's professional orientation in higher education. Acquiring communicative competence in higher education influences the graduate's competitiveness in the labor market and their successful socialization in the future.

Teachers must adopt a cognitive-pragmatic approach—guiding students to think, explore, and express their judgments based on their observations—rather than merely imparting knowledge. However, in many observed lessons, teachers often allow independent inquiry by students only during educational games. At other times, the teacher explains the lesson's core content, delivering it in a ready-made form as defined in the curriculum and textbooks.

The main factors influencing the development of communicative competence in students include social demand, state standards, the educational institution's learning environment, continuity in education, pedagogical support, motivation for developing communicative competence, integrative connections, teaching resources, organizational forms, and teaching methods.

Using the principle of continuity in developing communicative competence involves aligning educational programs to ensure coordination across stages, from initial preparation to post-graduate education. It assumes that the "exit" from one program naturally transitions into the "entry" of another. In a system of continuous education, it is essential to standardize all programs from start to finish based on shared objectives across all systems.

In higher education, the development of students' communicative competence is implemented across all disciplines (humanities, natural sciences, professional subjects, as well as extracurricular activities).

The content of humanities expands students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in constructing oral and written texts. Natural sciences, on the other hand, involve a high level of generalization and emphasize cause-and-effect relationships, which contribute to the enhancement of knowledge essential for developing communicative competence.

In higher education, didactic materials should be based on a didactic principle that incorporates communicative activity, learner engagement, interactive participation, tasks, and competence-based activities.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, the new educational standards and subject curricula introduced into our country's continuous education system are closely linked to the formation and improvement of students' communicative abilities. This connection promises significant changes in the future. Their successful implementation depends on how well the main actors of the education system—teachers and students—understand their assigned tasks, their commitment to fulfilling them diligently, and the ability of each subject specialist to reveal the communicative aspects of their respective disciplines.

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